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INGENIOUS: AN EDUCATIONAL GAME TEACHING MULTIDISCIPLINARY PRODUCT DESIGN AND DEVELOPMENT PROJECT CHOICES

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ABSTRACT

While design is widely considered to be a core or distinguishing activity of engineering and probably the most common kind of problem regularly solved by engineers, teaching product design and development (PDD) is a challenge. The different engineering disciplines in a multidisciplinary PDD team use different tools and techniques (T&T) to support their work, where different T&T combinations might fit the development and new T&T are being developed every day. Choosing promising T&T during each PDD phase is therefore an important learning goal. With this motivation, this paper presents the Ingenious game. The paper explains the theoretical background that supported developing the game, describes the game elements and mechanics, presents how its is intended to be used for gamifying a

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PDD course, and validates the game against the best practices found in the literature.

1 INTRODUCTION

Design problems are typically the most complex and ill structured of all problems, for which solutions are performed through an iterative process of decision making and model building [1]. Complex and open problems, also called wicked problems, typically require the integration of several content domains, thus taking on an interdisciplinary nature [1] [2]. As a result, teaching product design and development (PDD) can be a challenge.

The different engineering disciplines in a multidisciplinary PDD team use unique tools and techniques (T&T) to support their work, where different T&T combinations might fit the development and new T&T are being developed every day. Choosing promising T&T during each PDD phase is therefore an important learning goal. Creating their own mental model can help the students in determining promising T&T to solve the problem. The challenge, therefore, includes (1) covering the content related to the general design and development process, (2) the content from each involved discipline, and (3) also provide a meaningful relation among them, while (4) preventing that the students from one discipline lose their interest when the presented T&T are from another discipline.

Based on the author's experience it can be said that trying to fit this content into a traditional higher education PDD master course has resulted in limiting students' learning experience. The courses and related projects either deliver a broad and superficial presentation of the entire design process, or a deep and narrow analysis of one phase or discipline; both are not sufficient for teaching PDD through a course dynamic that resembles the real engineering practice.

For solving this problem, Pereira Pessoa et al. [3] proposes a gamification-based pedagogical approach, which integrates Just-in-Time-Learning (JIT-Learning) and flipped-classroom in a project-based learning (PjBL) setting. The gamified project creates the scenario (set of specific tasks/problems) for the just-in-time pulling of learning content supported by the flipped-classroom, where the students will learn as needed to perform the project. This paper presents the background for this gamification setting, describes the created game for supporting the gamification and reflects on its capabilities.

2 THEORETICAL BACKGROUND

According to Huizinga [4] "playing is older than culture and is at the very center of what makes us human". When reflecting on Huizinga's work Tekinbaş and Zimmerman [5] conclude that play creates an artificial space beyond that of ordinary life, where meaning emerges from what is "at play". Indeed, "the goal of successful game design is the creation of meaningful play" [5]. Meaning emerges from the game setting and rules, which is what differs simple play from a game.

The form of a game can vary, although an approach by Miller and Cliff [6] characterizes games in relation to several dimensions of complexity: number of players ("single-person", "two-person" and "n-person"); number of movements

(moves); continuity of the strategy space (discrete or continuous); scoring structure (“zero-sum” or “non zero-sum”); information structure (perfect or imperfect); and symmetry of strategies (symmetric or asymmetric). Games can also be classified according to their application [7]; namely leisure games designed with the sole objective of entertaining, serious games with purposes other than or additional to entertainment, and learning games which are designed with specific learning goals in mind.

2.1 Conflicts of interest and games theory

The study of conflict of interest was formalized, initially, by game theory: Von Neumann and Morgenstern [8] proposed ways to study and predict the performance of rational agents, in a competitive context of defined rules. Thus, it is possible to calculate an expectation of minimizing losses for each opponent during the game. In addition, they presented the possibility of coalition, where two or more individuals come together, to maximize their gains, thus presenting cooperation and competition. Consequently, game theory is about finding the best strategy for playing a game according to the defined (and not defined) rules.

2.2 Gamification

Gamification is the use of game elements and game-design techniques in non-game contexts, thoughtfully applying typical game-like elements to real-world or productive activities [9] [10][11][12]. Important to note is this approach does not require a self-contained “game”. The success of gamification relies on the power of the motivation to induce desired actions. Chou proposed a gamification design framework called Octalysis, which includes eight core drives, that function as prerequisites for fostering motivation, and triggering the planned behavior [10]: (1) **Epic Meaning & Calling** refers to when people believe they are doing something greater than themselves; (2) **Development & Accomplishment** that drives performing better, developing skills and achieving mastery; (3) **Empowerment of Creativity & Feedback** for players engaging in a creative process; (4) **Ownership & Possession** motivates players by the feeling they own or control something; (5) **Social Influence & Relatedness** incorporates the social elements that motivate people; (6) **Scarcity & Impatience** drives wanting something simply because it is difficult to reach; (7) **Unpredictability & Curiosity** creates engagement because of the uncertainty of what comes next; and (8) **Loss & Avoidance** is the motivation to avoid a negative consequence.

2.3 Games and gamification in engineering design and development

Games, gamification, and game theory are distinct, and thus have different implications for education. Games are normally self-contained, played individually or in groups, and can include collaborative and/or competitive elements. Gamification would be integrated with other class activities, potentially as part of individual or group activities, which can include collaboration, and/or competition elements, thereby the teacher makes the class itself a game [13]. Finally, game theory finds

optimal strategies according to the constraints set by the rules. It is usually taught as part of a course's content than used as a pedagogical approach.

Hartmann and Gommer [14] argue that, although educational games have the potential to enhance intrinsic motivation in students, other motivational approaches are necessary also to justify the reasons for including the game in the teaching environment. Hernández-Fernández et al. [15] state that the students' perceived learning from the games is related to the link between game and course discussions after game play, a realistic game content and the students' prior knowledge. By reflecting on these authors' findings, it is possible to conclude that gamification is more promising in the case of wicked problems (such as design), since they benefit from combination of different pedagogical methods.

According to Sánchez-Mena and Martí-Parreño [13] the four main gamification drivers are attention-motivation, entertainment, interactivity, and ease of learning, while the four main barriers are lack of resources, students' apathy, subject fit, and classroom dynamics. Djelil et al. state that a well-designed learning game should be useful from a pedagogical point of view, usable from a learner point of view and acceptable from the institution, the teacher/trainer and the learner points of views. Table 1 summarizes the aspects that motivate and demotivate the students/players according to Hartmann and Gommer [14] and Djelil et al. [16].

Table 1. *Students/players motivating and demotivating aspects.*

Motivational aspects (M)	Demotivational aspects (D)
<p>M1. Clear instructions.</p> <p>M2. Have specific and clear goals that match with the instructional objectives describing the targeted skills and knowledge.</p> <p>M3. Including different difficulty levels and other instructional methods can address students' knowledge variance.</p> <p>M4. Right challenge of the game content.</p> <p>M5. Engagement through interaction.</p> <p>M6. Competition between teams.</p> <p>M7. Direct feedback on performance.</p> <p>M8. Have an internal representational world, which may also include metaphors and narration.</p> <p>M9. Appropriate and progressive difficulty levels.</p> <p>M10. Learners should be encouraged to persevere despite failure. Failures and mistakes have no real-world consequences, they are rather turned into learning moments where learners must question and explore different options to achieve their tasks.</p> <p>M11. The learner can make decisions and set strategies when solving problems and performing tasks.</p>	<p>D1. Instructions difficult to understand.</p> <p>D2. Too difficult or too easy game tasks.</p> <p>D3. Game tasks do not match students' current level of knowledge.</p> <p>D4. Insufficient time for finishing rounds or could not contribute due to large teams.</p>

When searching the literature for learning games and gamification initiatives aiming specifically to PDD, several examples were identified, but none fully approached the problem stated in the introduction. [17] [18] [19] [20] [21] [22]. The game proposed by O'Sullivan and Sheahan [23] is the one that most resembles what is intended in this paper. They created a board game-like toolkit which allows the students to play through an example of a new product development to understand the process and

the tools, before using it for their own product development efforts. A complimentary website is used to enhance the physical toolkit, and it provides more examples of the tools being used.

3 THE INGENIOUS GAME

The Ingenious Game was originally developed for the gamification of a first semester Mechanical and Industrial Design engineering master course. During the course, the students define a design development process fitting to a given product/system development scenario. The process definition must include and integrate the content related to (1) the design and development process's phases; (2) the best practices covering the design and development process areas; (3) the different development models that help organizing the design and development according to the specific aspects from the solution to be developed; and (4) the specific tools and techniques used by the diverse disciplines that can be involved during the development.

Defining the design and development process to be used in a particular scenario is an open problem, these problems' underlying uncertainty and ambiguity require critical thinking and creativity from the solvers [24]. Consequently, the course must give relevance and meaning to the previously mentioned content, so the students can create a mental model for integrating it according to the constraints from a given design and development project. As a result, the gamified course has the following learning objectives (LO), where LO1, 2, 3 and 6 are specific to the game. At the end of the course the students are capable to:

- LO1. Select the appropriate development model according to the product complexity and development risks.
- LO2. Select the appropriate design techniques according to the development process phase and the involved engineering disciplines.
- LO3. Design a product development process based on the complexity and inherent risks from the solution to be developed.
- LO4. Deconstruct the rationale for choosing the development model and or selecting the design techniques.
- LO5. Reflect on the results from the selected development model, design techniques and the resulting performance from the created design and development process.
- LO6. Carry out a collaborative project.
- LO7. Judge trade-offs choices during a project execution.

In addition to the learning objectives, the game also fulfills the following requirements (R):

- R1. The game should be playable either standalone or as part of a course gamification.
- R2. The game should be an expandable, modular and flexible platform, that allows incorporating new engineering disciplines (i.e. chemical engineering technologies, tools, and techniques).

3.1 Game elements

The Ingenious card game includes the following elements (figure 1), where the Octalysis core drivers [10] are underlined in the descriptions:

- The **challenge scenario** describes the development challenge that give meaning to the game to be played.
- The **risk level** contributes to the sense of loss during the game, so loss avoidance is about keeping the risk level low. The initial risk level is indicated by the challenge scenario complexity, and the players development model choice (more complex developments are riskier, and therefore benefit from more iterations in the development process).
- The **risk dice** adds an element of unpredictability. They are rolled for each issue card to check if its related risk occurs. The result that triggers the risk varies according to the actual risk level.
- The **annotation board** helps the team keep track of the progress, it includes information about the initial and actual risk levels, the initial and actual budget, and the planned and performed iterations. By visually representing the group's accomplishment the board helps create social pressure.
- The **budget** is the amount of money available for the team to acquire techniques and best practice cards. Budget is also needed to play the bought cards during the game rounds, which represent the cost to acquire and apply the knowledge. The team receives an initial budget and additional budget is released after successfully finishing a development phase (game round). The budget adds elements of loss avoidance, scarcity, and accomplishment to the game.
- The **engineer cards** represents the engineering disciplines playing the game (mechanical, electrical, software etc.), and needed to solve the challenge scenario. These cards provide meaning and a sense of ownership. Each player in the team has a card and some techniques are more effective if acquired and played by specific engineers.
- The **tool and technique cards** represent design and development tools and techniques and show their capability to solve development issues according to their characteristics. The tools and techniques contributes to the sense of ownership, as they are not the team's property, but the property of each engineer that unlocked (learned) and acquired them, and only these engineers can play the technique during a round.
- The **best practice cards** guarantee that the widely accepted best practices for PDD are also included in the game. Like the tools and technique cards, these cards help solving issues.
- The **issue cards** represent typical issues from each design and development phase. A certain number of cards is randomly drawn in each round, which contributes to the game's unpredictability. To solve an issue card, the player needs to be playing a technique which the characteristics' values are equal or higher than the ones required by the issue. Each issue card also includes a risk, which may be triggered depending on the risk dice results.

Figure 1. Ingenious game and gamification elements.

To fulfill the previously stated R2, the game has a modular architecture. New challenge scenarios can be added and align the game to different courses. New engineering cards, tools and technique cards and issue cards can also be added as expansions to the base game (i.e., cards related to chemical engineering challenges). Figure 2 shows a technique and an issue card sample. To solve an issue a technique must have matching stats and have traits with values equal or superior from the issue. Adding new cards require maintaining the matching and making sure that new issues are solvable using the existing techniques.

Figure 2. Technique and issue cards example.

Besides the game itself, the gamification setting includes a Wiki, an assessment portal, and a results board (figure 1). In the Wiki, the students can get further knowledge about the engineering tools and techniques included in the game, and that support their decision on which tools and techniques to acquire and play during each game round. The assessment portal includes quiz questions that cover all the tools and techniques, so successfully answering the quizzes can be used for unlocking the specific tool or technique before they become available to acquire and play. Finally, the result board displays the results (actual budget, risk level and number of performed iterations) of the teams, thereby increasing the social pressure and sense of accomplishment.

As a note, in relation to the Octalysis core drivers, empowerment was the only driver not included. Since the game was envisioned to be played only once over the span of a course, it was not possible to represent the teams gaining experience (climbing the techniques' learning curves), this could be solved in the case of playing multiple times, but it is outside of the scope of this work.

3.2 Game mechanics

When using the game to support the course gamification, the objective is to mimic a product design and development process execution during a new product development project. In the course setting, besides gamification, the other teaching strategies were a flipped classroom and just-in-time learning. No content is to be given beforehand, as the game's challenge requires that the students learn the theoretical content to progress in the game. Therefore, while going through the gamified project's phases, the students must select the knowledge delivered 'just-in-time' along side learning in a flipped classroom.

Figure 3 shows the game and the gamification mechanics using a simplified sequence diagram [25], which includes the gamified course activities sequence and the game activities sequence. The game activities and some of the gamification activities take place once in each round. In summary, the lecturer delivers the game briefing when the game rules and challenge are presented, and the students define the quantity of iterations they will execute during the upcoming game round 3 (more iterations mean reduced risk level, but there is an overhead cost of iterating). In each of the four game rounds (1. conceptual design, 2. system design, 3. detail design, and 4. system integration and test) the competing groups of students must select the tools and techniques to learn in the Wiki, unlock the tools and techniques by answering the quizzes, acquire the tools and techniques, define the hand (group of tools and techniques) to be played in the round, draw and solve the challenges (also considering the actual risk level and rolling the risk dice), and go to the next round/phase or repeat/rework the round, if the remaining unsolved issues do not allow progressing.

Figure 3. Ingenious game and gamification mechanics

At the end of each round, the students reflect on the rationale behind the strategy they set, the effectiveness of their choices, and what and why they would make differently in a similar situation in the future. The lecturer then gives feedback based on the students' reflection. After the four rounds, the final activity is to evaluate the students' work. Summative assessment is based on the reflections' quality and not on the game results.

4 DISCUSSION

At the current state, and before the Ingenious game and the design and development course gamifications strategy is used in a real course, they were validated against the literature by describing it according to the mentioned classification and by checking its coverage of the Octalysis drivers and on how it considers the motivational and demotivational aspects listed in table 1.

The Ingenious game is a learning card game that can be classified as: (1) n-person game, where the game can be played by just one group, where the members collaborate, or can be played with several groups, where the groups compete; (2) non zero-sum, since all the players can get partial scores; (3) with discrete movements with asymmetrical and discrete strategies, since it includes four rounds representing the PDD, when the players have a discrete number of cards available to play.

The Ingenious game covers, to some extent, all core drivers from Octalysis model, except empowerment. Empowerment can be added if the game is played as a

sequence of scenarios during which the engineers get more proficient with the tools the more frequently they are used. Such applications though are outside this work scope.

Considering the motivational and demotivational aspects previously presented, the Ingenious game has an internal representation of the design process and the related elements (M8), has goals that match with the learning objectives (M2), fosters engagement through interaction with the team members (M5), whenever there is more than one team it includes the competition between the teams (M6), gives freedom to the learners making their own decisions (M11), provides direct feedback on the teams' performance by calculating each round's results (M7), and learners are encouraged to persevere despite of failure (M10). This last aspect is further emphasized by the gamification setting, since grading is based on the reflection related to both successes and failures.

Other aspects need to be further investigated through a pilot game and gamification runs, which includes the instructions clarity (M1/D1), challenge alignment between the course and the game (M4), the addressing of the students' knowledge variance (M3/D3), the difficulty level appropriateness and progressiveness (M9/D2), and the appropriate amount of time and team size (D4). Finally, the gamification capacity to deliver the LOs needs to be validated by offering the course and getting students feedback

5 SUMMARY AND ACKNOWLEDGMENTS

This paper presented the Ingenious game, which has been developed to teach PDD, and particularly the choice of techniques to be used during each PDD phase. Both the proposed game and gamification concepts were explained in terms of covering the Octalysis gamification model drivers and on tackling the motivation and demotivation aspects that affect learning games.

Seven out of the eight Octalysis drivers were covered, where only empowerment could not be considered: the game was envisioned to be played only once during a course, and it was not possible to represent the teams gaining experience, since different techniques are expected to be played in each round. Although the motivation and demotivation aspects seem to be approached, their validation require a practical application of the game. Consequently, the next step would be to put the game into practice during the master course for Mechanical Engineering and Industrial Design Engineering students, which will provide empirical validation of the game.

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